

Effect of Management Support and Information Technology on Employee's Empowerment and Innovative Work Behaviors (Case Study of dr. Zainoel Abidin District Hospital Banda Aceh)

Junaidi¹, Amri², and Teuku Roli Ilhamsyah³

¹⁾ *Magister of Management Post-Graduate Study, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh, Indonesia*

^{2,3)} *Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh, Indonesia*

Abstract

Innovative work behavior is likely to be an important need for the increasing performance of the hospital to provide the health public services. Theoretically and empirically, the behaviors be related to employee perception on management support, information technology and employee empowerment. The study aims to determine the effect of management supports and information technology on employee empowerment as well as their impact on the innovative work behaviors of the employee of dr. Zainoel Abidin District Hospital Banda Aceh. The study conducted of 302 employees of the hospital. The data collected by questionnaire and then the data is analyzed by statistical means of structural equation model (SEM). The study found that management support and information technology have a positive and significant effect on the employee empowerment and innovative work behavior. The employee empowerment mediates the effect of management supports and information technology on the innovative work behavior.

Keywords: Innovative Work Behaviors, Employee Empowerment, Management supports and Information Technology

I. INTRODUCTION

Improving the performance of public institutions such as regional hospitals is a must for every local government. This is due to the increasing public demand for public health services from year to year. Along with the increase in population, the need for hospital services is also increasing (Husaini et al., 2017). Employees are the hospital's main resource. So that the hospital's performance in providing services is largely determined by the work behavior of its employees. Work behavior is related to the form of behavior and attitudes of employees in carrying out the work assigned to them. With increasingly complex hospital services, it requires innovative work behavior from employees as the main resource for organizing public services in hospitals. Innovative work behavior is a form of behavior that aims to achieve initiation and the introduction of ideas, processes, procedures and new products that are useful for organizations in the context of this research company (De Jong & Hartog, 2010). This behavior consists of four dimensions which are part of the overall innovative work behavior. The four dimensions are idea exploration, idea generation, idea coalition building or idea championing and idea implementation (Klysen & Street, in De Jong & Hartog, 2010).

Efforts to form innovative work behavior among hospital employees can be done in various ways including employee empowerment. Employee empowerment can be interpreted as giving autonomy, authority, trust, and encouraging individuals in an organization to develop regulations in order to complete work (Sadarusman, 2004). Empowerment of employees is believed to be able to have a positive impact on innovative work behavior. The relationship between employee empowerment and innovative work behavior is caused by employees who feel empowered in the workplace will tend to have a positive attitude towards the work assigned, so that innovative behavior emerges for the completion of the task.

In addition to empowering employees, other factors that can influence innovative work behavior are management support and information technology. Management support relates to how far the management provides clear communication, assistance, and support to its subordinates in carrying out their assigned tasks (Tangkilisan, 2007: 18). Furthermore, information technology infrastructure can be defined as the foundation of information technology capabilities (Weill et al., 2006). Information technology capability is defined as the ability to mobilize and disseminate information technology based on resources by combining it with other resources or capital. This information technology capability includes internal technical (equipment, software, and cabling) and human expertise needed to provide reliable services (McKay & Brockway, 2009).

Both management support and information technology can not only have an impact on innovative work behavior but also can affect the perception of employee empowerment. The relationship between management support and perceptions of empowerment due to management support makes employees feel empowered according to their workability. Management support for the implementation of work by employees not only makes employees work more comfortably but can also lead to positive perceptions regarding their existence in the organization. They feel empowered and valued at work.

Furthermore, the relationship between information technology and employee empowerment can be explained that the existence of information technology can encourage employees to work better so that perceptions of employee empowerment also increase. The better the information technology available, the better the work will be done by employees so that the existence of information technology can make them feel more empowered in the workplace.

Zainoel Abidin District Hospital (whereby: RSUZA) Banda Aceh is a public institution that is expected to provide health services for all Acehnese people. The existence of these hospitals has a very important role in meeting the community's need for health services. In carrying out its operational activities, the hospital has 2,436 employees who are distributed in 7 types of workforce. The type of workforce in question consists of specialist doctors, general practitioners, dentists, nurses, other health personnel, administrative staff, and clerical personnel. So far, the Aceh government has sought to improve the service performance of the hospital in serving the needs of the community. However, the performance of hospital services is certainly related to innovative work behavior that is owned by all employees. Innovative work behavior will be able to bring up ideas and service innovations in order to accelerate the implementation of public services to meet the community's need for health services.

As explained earlier, both management support and information technology not only affect employee empowerment but can also have an impact on innovative work behavior. So that the existence of employee empowerment can be used as an intervening variable between innovative work behavior and management support and information technology. Therefore, this study analyzes the influence of management support and information technology on the innovative work behavior of hospital employees by placing employee empowerment as a mediating variable.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 The link between management support and employee's empowerment

Management support is an activity that impacts, directs and maintains human behavior in the organization (Dewi, 2013). Management support in an organization can build on employee empowerment. This is because management support is usually directed so that employees can carry out their duties properly so that organizational goals can be achieved in accordance with the targets set. Management support aims to make sure that employees can work well so that these conditions have a direct impact on employee empowerment. This is in accordance with the opinion of Tangkilisan (2007) which states that management support is related to how far the management provides clear communication, assistance, and support to subordinates in carrying out the tasks charged. In empirical research, the relationship between management support and employee empowerment is evidenced by the research of Al-Shaar et al. (2015) that management support has a positive and significant impact on employee empowerment. The better management support, the better the empowerment of employees. This is due to the achievement of organizational goals by management involving employees as their main resource.

Referring to the explanation above, the first hypothesis as follows:

H₁: Management support has a significant effect on the employee's empowerment of RSUZA Banda Aceh

2.2 The link between information technology and employee's empowerment

Empowerment of employees in the workplace related to information technology. This is because information technology can facilitate the implementation of work by employees. The influence of empirical information technology and employee empowerment has been proven by the findings of the research by Malafe et al. (2017) conclude that there is a relationship between information technology and employee empowerment in the workplace. Previously, Qudah & Melhem (2011) also found that information technology had a positive effect on employee empowerment.

Based on the description above, it is clear that information technology can influence employee empowerment. The better information technology the better the empowerment of employees. This is due to the availability of information technology encourages the employees in carrying out the work assigned to them. Referring to the explanation above, the second hypothesis as follows:

H₂: Information technology has a significant effect on the employees empowerment of RSUZA Banda Aceh.

2.3 The link between management support and innovative work behavior

Management support can affect employee work behavior. Employee assessment of management support can have an impact on workplace behavior. When management support is perceived well by employees, then they will tend to be serious in carrying out the work charged. One manifestation of work behavior as an impact of a good assessment of management support is innovative work behavior. In this case, employees strive to innovate, especially related to the method or method of carrying out the work they value more effectively and efficiently. The influence of management support on innovative work behavior as found by Al-Shaar et al. (2015) that management support can have an impact on positively improving innovative work behavior and employee performance. The research study of Amri (2018) using secondary data is also proves that wages as a form of management support can encourage improvement in employee behavior in the workplace.

Referring to the explanation above, the third hypothesis as follows:

H₃: Management support has a significant effect on the innovative work behavior of the employee of RSUZA Banda Aceh.

2.4 The link between information technology and innovative work behavior

Studies on the impact of information technology on human behavior have been carried out by previous researchers (Amri & Surya, 2013). The information technology is very important for the smooth implementation of duties by every employee, especially employees of government agencies. This is due to the implementation of duties by employees usually supported by information technology infrastructure such as computers, for example, tasks that are directly related to the implementation of public services to meet community needs, as well as office administration tasks. Until now, generally, government agencies use information technology infrastructure to facilitate the implementation of their staff duties. So that the existence of information technology can encourage the emergence of innovative work behavior among employees so that their performance increases. The relationship between information technology and work behavior and employee performance is supported by the opinion of Guzman et al. (2015) which states that the use of information technology that is precisely supported by the expertise of the personnel who operate it can encourage the emergence of innovative work behavior and in turn have an impact on improving the performance of the employees concerned. Mazidi et al (2014) research also provide empirical evidence that information technology influences employee work behavior. Similarly, the findings of the research by Mano et al. (2014) also concluded that information technology has a positive and significant effect on innovation. Finally, the findings of Matata & Namusonge (2015) research also provide empirical evidence of the influence of information technology on innovative work behavior and company performance.

Referring to the explanation above, the fourth hypothesis as follows:

H₄: Information technology has a significant effect on the innovative work behavior of the employee of RSUZA Banda Aceh

2.5 The link between employee's empowerment and innovative work behavior

Empowerment can have an effect on innovative work behavior because employees have a feeling of having greater work outcomes and initiatives. Spreitzer et al. (2008) prove the existence of a positive and significant relationship between empowerment and innovative work behavior. Research findings Mathieu et al. (2006) also showed a positive relationship between empowerment and innovative work behavior. Similarly, Kirkman et al. (2014) in their study also found that empowerment can encourage employees to work better characterized by the emergence of innovative behavior in the workplace.

In line with the findings of several researchers above, Imam & Hassan (2015) also found that employee empowerment had a positive and significant effect on work behavior. The better the empowerment of employees, the better work behavior, and empowerment can encourage the emergence of innovative work behavior in employees.

Referring to the explanation above, the fifth hypothesis as follows:

H₅: Employee's empowerment has a significant effect on the innovative work behavior of the employee of RSUZA Banda Aceh.

In accordance with the formulation of the problem and the purpose of the study, can be understood that this study uses four variables including innovative work behavior, employee empowerment, management support, and information technology. Innovative work behavior and employee empowerment act as endogenous variables. On the other hand, management support and information technology act as exogenous variables. In this case, employee empowerment is also placed as an intervening variable between innovative work behavior on the one hand, and

management support and information technology on other. Therefore, the paradigm or framework of relationships between variables in this study as shown in Figure 1

Figure 1
Research Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The study was conducted at RSUZA Banda Aceh. The research sample of 302 employees of the hospital was taken by purposive and proportional sampling. The questionnaire was used as the main instrument for data collection. The questionnaire contains a number of statements relating to management support, information technology, employee empowerment, and innovative work behavior. Each statement is provided with alternative answers in the level form of agreement (agree to disagree). The scale of measurement used in this study is the Likert scale with interval 1-5. Scoring is intended to give scores to each alternative level of agreement with the provisions score 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree and 5 = strongly agree. Then, the data is analyzed using statistical equipment structural equation model (SEM)-Amos.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 The result of Confirmatory Factor Analysis test and Measurement Model

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is designed to test the multidimensionality of a theoretical construct. This analysis is often also called testing the validity of theoretical constructs. The benchmark used is the value of loading factors. An indicator is declared valid if it has a value of loading factor > 0.70. Conversely, if the value of the loading factor < 0.70 then the indicator is declared invalid to measure the construct (Ghozali, 2011). Another benchmark in assessing the significance of factor weights is the critical ratio (CR). This is intended to measure whether the indicators in each construct are significantly the dimensions of the construct, provided that CR > 2.00 and p-value < 0.05 can be interpreted that the indicators are significant dimensions of the construct being measured.

The test is carried out up to three stages. In the first stage, there are several indicators that are declared not feasible in measuring variables so that the indicator is reduced from the model. Furthermore, in the second stage, there are also a number of indicators which are reduced from the model. Finally, in the third stage, all indicators have been declared feasible because they have a loading factor > 0.70. Along with the CFA test, a measurement model test was also conducted. In the test, the benchmarks of the goodness of fit are some statistical criteria such as Chi-square, Significance Probability, GFI, AGFI, CFI, TLI, and RMSEA. The model is stated to meet the criteria of goodness of fit also after the third stage.

4.2 The result of full Structural Model

After the test of CFA and goodness of fit as proxies of the measurement model, it is seen that each indicator can be used to define a latent construct, the next step in using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) as a data analysis tool is to conduct a structural test of the entire model. In this case, the researcher directly tests the relationship between all the

variables (constructs) studied by involving all indicators in each construct. The results of the full structural model explain the relationship between all research variables as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2
The Result of SEM Full Structural Model

Figure 2 above does not only show the value of the path coefficient of each exogenous latent variable towards endogenous latent variables but also shows the value of the manifest variable for each latent variable. The results of the full structural model show the value of the estimate coefficients of each exogenous construct (management support and information technology) towards endogenous constructs (employee empowerment and innovative work behavior) as shown in Table 1.

Tabel 1. Inter Variable Estimation Coefficient

		Estimate Coefficient	C.R.	P-Value	Hypothesis
Employee's Empowerment	<--- Information Technology	.727	11.156	***	Accepted
Employee's Empowerment	<--- Management Support	.149	2.497	.013	Accepted
Innovative Work behavior	<--- Employee's Empowerment	.269	2.485	.013	Accepted
Innovative Work behavior	<--- Management Support	.473	6.472	***	Accepted
Innovative Work behavior	<--- Information Technology	.110	2.725	.002	Accepted

Source : Primary Data (Processed), 2019

*** denotes for the significant at 99% level.

Based on the table above, the discussion of the influence between variables as represented in the following section.

4.3 Analysis of the Effect of Management Support on Employee Empowerment

Management support is a positive and significant effect on employee empowerment, indicated by the estimated coefficient value of 0.149 with a p-value of 0.013. Referring to the estimated coefficient, the direct effect of management support for employee empowerment is 2.22 percent. This means that employees who have a good perception of management support in their work will also have a good assessment of employee empowerment. With management support, they will feel empowered at work. Conversely, when management support is perceived as not good, then it has an impact on reducing their perception of empowerment.

Referring to the explanation above, the first hypothesis (H₁) which states the management support has a significant effect on the employee's empowerment of RSUZA Banda Aceh accepted. This finding is consistent with the results of Al-Shaar et al (2015) study which concluded that management support had a positive and significant impact on employee's empowerment.

4.4 Analysis of the Effect of Information Technology on Employee Empowerment

Information technology also has a positive and significant effect on employee empowerment, indicated by an estimated coefficient of 0.727 with a p-value of 0.001. The direct influence of information technology on employee empowerment is 52.85 percent. This means that the existence of information technology can make employees feel empowered in the workplace. The better information technology, the better the perception of empowerment. The existence of a unidirectional relationship between the availability of information technology and the perception of employees on empowerment is caused, information technology is very important for employees in carrying out the work assigned to them. Without information technology, it can cause difficulties for them to work. Even some medical jobs, for example, cannot be implemented without information technology. This is what causes information technology to have a real influence on employee empowerment..

Referring to the explanation above, the second hypothesis (H₂) which states that the information technology has a significant effect on the employees empowerment of RSUZA Banda Aceh accepted. This finding supports the research findings conducted by Qudah & Melhem (2011) and Malafe et al. (2017) that also concluded that information technology has a positive effect on employee empowerment.

4.5 Analysis of the Effect of Management Support on Innovative Work Behaviors

Management support has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behavior, indicated by an estimated coefficient of 0.473 and a p-value of 0.006. The direct effect of management support on innovative work behavior is 22.37. Employees who have a relatively good assessment of management support will tend to have innovative work behavior that is also relatively good. The better management supports the better the innovative work behavior. In other words, employees who feel they receive management support in carrying out their work will tend to be more innovative in their work compared to employees who feel they lack management support.

Referring to the explanation above, then the third hypothesis (H₃) which states the management support has a significant effect on the innovative work behavior of the employee of RSUZA Banda Aceh accepted. This finding is in line with the results of Spreitzer et al. (2008) that proves the existence of a positive and significant relationship between empowerment and innovative work behavior. Research findings Mathieu et al. (2006) also showed a positive relationship between empowerment and innovative work behavior. Similarly, Kirkman et al. (2014) in their study also found that empowerment can encourage employees to work better characterized by the emergence of innovative behavior in the workplace.

4.6 Analysis of the Effect of Information Technology on Innovative Work Behaviors

Information technology is positively and significantly influences innovative work behaviors. This indicated by the estimated coefficient value of 0.110 with a p-value of 0.002 <0.05. The direct influence of information technology on innovative work behavior is 1.21 percent. This thing means that the better the employee's assessment of the availability of information technology, the better the innovative work behavior. Information technology can directly have a positive impact on the tendency of employees to innovate in completing the work which is assigned to them..

The better the assessment of empowerment the higher the tendency to behave innovatively. Conversely, employees with poor perceptions of empowerment will tend to be less or not innovative at work. Thus the results of this study provide empirical evidence of a unidirectional relationship between employee empowerment and innovative work behavior.

Referring to the explanation above, the fourth hypothesis (H₄) which states that the information technology has a significant effect on the innovative work behavior of the employee of RSUZA Banda Aceh accepted. This study found that management support and information technology can positively and significantly improve innovative work behavior among the employees of RSUZA Banda Aceh. This finding is in line with the results of previous studies conducted by Al-Shaar et al. (2015) that management support can encourage the emergence of innovative work behavior, and research by Mano et al. (2014) and Matata & Namusonge (2015) who also concluded that information technology has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behaviors

4.7 Effect Analysis of Employee's Empowerment on Innovative Work Behaviors

Employee empowerment has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behavior. This is indicated by the estimated coefficient value of 0.269 with a p-value of 0.013 <0.05. The direct effect of employee empowerment on innovative work behavior of 7.24 percent. This can be interpreted that the better the employee's assessment of their empowerment in the workplace, the better innovative work behavior will be. Those who feel empowered at work will be encouraged to innovate in carrying out the work they are charged with. The better the assessment of empowerment the higher the tendency to behave innovatively. Conversely, employees with poor perceptions of empowerment will tend to be less or not innovative at work, so that the results of this study provide empirical evidence of a unidirectional relationship between employee empowerment and innovative work behaviors.

Referring to the explanation above, then the fifth hypothesis (H5) which states the employee's empowerment has a significant effect on the innovative work behavior of the employee of RSUZA Banda Aceh accepted. The existence of a positive and significant influence of employee empowerment on innovative work behavior as described earlier, in accordance with the opinion of Spreitzer et al. (2008) which states that empowerment is positively related to innovative work behavior. Empirically, Kirkman et al. (2014) in their study also found that empowerment can encourage employees to work better characterized by the emergence of innovative behavior in the workplace

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSIONS

1. Management support and information technology have a positive and significant effect on employee empowerment at RSUZA Banda Aceh. Employees who have a good perception of management support will tend to feel empowered in the workplace. Conversely, when management support is deemed lacking, the condition has an impact on decreasing perceptions of empowerment. In other words, poor management support can cause employees to feel not or less empowered. The better the information technology the better their perceptions of empowerment. Conversely, poor information technology can have a negative impact on perceptions of empowerment. This implicitly means that information technology is an important determinant of employee empowerment in the hospital..
2. Management support and information technology have a positive and significant effect on employees' innovative work behavior. The better management support, the greater the tendency of employees to behave innovatively in the workplace. Conversely, when management support is considered not good, the condition will adversely affect innovative work behavior. The better information technology the better innovative work behavior. Conversely, when information technology is perceived as not good, then these conditions have a negative impact on innovative work behavior..
3. Employee's empowerment has a positive and significant effect on employees' innovative work behavior. Employees who feel empowered at work will have innovative work behavior that is better than employees who are not empowered in the workplace. Conversely, when empowerment is considered to be poor or there is no empowerment at all, then this condition can be a barrier to the emergence of innovative work behavior.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Referring to the conclusions outlined above, the recommendations and recommendations of this study are as follows:

1. The leader of the RSUZA Banda Aceh is deemed necessary to improve management support in all areas of duty at the hospital. Improved management support can be realized by providing moral support for every employee in carrying out their work, fulfilling the needs of employees in the workplace by providing sufficient work facilities for each employee. In addition, management must also be willing to help resolve problems faced by employees in the workplace..
2. The leader of the RSUZA Banda Aceh must try to increase the availability of information technology in the hospital. Improvement of information technology can be done through the provision of hospital software so that all the needs of the hospital are sufficient. In addition, RSUZA must also be able to strive for professional employees in dealing with IT problems that can arise in certain conditions.
3. The leader of the RSUZA Banda Aceh must improve employee empowerment in the workplace. Efforts to empower employees can be realized by giving awards to employees for the work they do to support the operation of the hospital. In addition, the clarity of the authority of the functions and responsibilities of each employee must also be increased so that they can work independently in accordance with the responsibilities given.

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